

“CAROL I” NATIONAL DEFENCE UNIVERSITY

PROCEEDINGS

Volume XIX

PROCEEDINGS
of the 19th Edition of

INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
“STRATEGIES XXI”

June 27-28, 2023

“CAROL I” NATIONAL DEFENCE UNIVERSITY PUBLISHING HOUSE
(Publishing house with recognized prestige validated by the National Council
for Attestation of University Degrees, Diplomas and Certificates)

“Carol I” National Defence University
Panduri Street no. 68-72, sector 5, 050622 Bucharest
Phone: 021 319 48 80 Fax: 021 319 48 66

ISSN 2971-8813
ISSN-L 2971-8813

SCIENTIFIC EDITORS:

Ștefan-Antonio DAN-ȘUTEU, PhD
Alexandru MUNTEANU-LUCINESCU-CASELLA, PhD
Daniel ROMAN, PhD
Dan-Lucian PETRESCU, PhD
Adi MUSTAȚĂ, PhD
Alba-Iulia Catrinel POPESCU, PhD

VOLUME XIX

R O M A N I A
MINISTRY OF NATIONAL DEFENCE
„CAROL I” National Defence University

PROCEEDINGS
INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
“STRATEGIES XXI”

Volume XIX

SCIENTIFIC EDITORS:

Ștefan-Antonio DAN-ȘUTEU, PhD

Alexandru MUNTEANU-LUCINESCU-CASELLA, PhD

Daniel ROMAN, PhD

Dan-Lucian PETRESCU, PhD

Adi MUSTAȚĂ, PhD

Alba Iulia Catrinel POPESCU, PhD

JUNE, 27-28
BUCHAREST, ROMANIA

TABLE OF CONTENTS

FOREWORD	10
-----------------------	----

SECTION 1: NEW DYNAMICS IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PRC ENGAGEMENT WITH LATIN AMERICA, AND CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE: COMPARISONS AND INSIGHTS	12
--	----

Robert Evan ELLIS

ROMANIAN DIPLOMACY IN THE CONTEXT OF REGIONAL SECURITY	31
---	----

Gabriel MICU

FROM CURRENCY WARS THROUGH TRADE WARS TO CONVENTIONAL WARS: REALIZATION OF OLD PREDICTIONS BEFORE OUR EYES	39
---	----

Przemysław FURGACZ

RUSSIA’S MILITARY AGGRESSION AND STRIKE IN GEORGIA ON AUGUST 2008: LESSONS LEARNED – GEOSTRATEGIC ANALYSIS	45
---	----

Vakhtang MAISAIA

SECTION 2: REGIONAL AND NATIONAL SECURITY

ON THE IMPERATIVE NEED TO ELIMINATE HYBRID THREATS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CURRENT CHANGES IN THE SECURITY ENVIRONMENT	55
---	----

Ivančik RADOSLAV

VIRTUAL ASSETS IN TIMES OF WAR: THE NATIONAL SECURITY IMPLICATIONS AND THE IMPERATIVE OF A NATIONAL DATA ANALYSIS PLATFORM, INVOLVING THE TRANSFER OF VALUE ACROSS BLOCKCHAINS	62
---	----

Bogdan VACUSTA

THE EXPANSION OF IRAN’S PROXY CAPABILITIES AND ITS IMPACT ON THE MILITARY INDUSTRY	70
---	----

Mihai VLAICU

EUROPEAN DEFENCE COOPERATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CONFLICT IN UKRAINE. ONE SMALL STEP FOR THE WORLD AND A GIANT LEAP FOR THE EUROPEAN UNION	79
---	----

Alin BODESCU

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE SOCIAL PROFILE OF GENERATION Z AND ITS ADAPTATION TO A MILITARY CAREER IN THE ROMANIAN ARMED FORCES	90
--	----

Cristian BOGANTOIU

**SECTION 5:
EUROPEAN SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE WAR OF AGGRESSION
AGAINST UKRAINE**

EXPLAINING THE PARTICIPATION OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION IN THE BLACK SEA GRAIN INITIATIVE. A CRITICAL ASSESEMNT OF PROMINENT RATIONALS ATTRIBUTED TO THIS DECISION..... 204

Alexandru LUCINESCU

SOME CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE GEOPOLITICS AND THE GEOSTRATEGY OF THE POST-COLD WAR PERIOD..... 224

*Anton MURARU
Cornel OANCEA*

THE THREAT OF A LARGE-SCALE LONG WAR OF AGGRESSION 236

Iulian CHIFU

BLACK SEA SECURITY ACT- A NEW PROGRAMATIC DOCUMENT THAT BRINGS THE BLACK SEA REGION INTO THE LIGHT..... 242

Andreea-Amalia STĂNICĂ

ASPECTS OF CONSIDERING DOMAINS, DIMENSIONS, AND ENVIRONMENTS MULTI-DOMAIN OPERATIONS' CONDUCT TO PRINCIPLES AND SPECIFITIES OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW..... 246

Luiza SÎRBU (RADUSLAV)

THE SPIRITUAL, PATRIOTIC, MORAL AND MATERIAL CONTRIBUTION OF THE MINISTERS OF THE HOLY ORTHODOX ALTARS TO THE SUPPORT OF ROMANIA'S EFFORTS IN THE WAR OF ALLIANCE 253

Constantin NEAGU

FORMULATING LONG-TERM STRATEGIC PRIORITIES IN THE NATIONAL SECURITY AND DEFENCE STRATEGY OF THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA – GEOSTRATEGIC SECURITY AND THE ROLE OF THE BLACK SEA 262

Mario MARINOV

**SECTION 6:
COGNITIVE WARFARE**

THE FAKE NEWS PHENOMENON. HISTORY, USE, DEFINITIONS, FORMS AND FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE ACCEPTANCE AND DISSEMINATION OF FAKE NEWS 273

Ioan-Cristian GHEORGHIU

IS GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE A BLACK SWAN IN COGNITIVE WARFARE?..... 284

Tudor URSEIU

THE IMPACT OF COGNITIVE WARFARE ON PLANNING AND DECISION-MAKING IN MILITARY CONFLICTS 289

Dănuț-Adrian ȘERBAN

EXPLAINING THE PARTICIPATION OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION IN THE BLACK SEA GRAIN INITIATIVE. A CRITICAL ASSESEMENT OF PROMINENT RATIONALS ATTRIBUTED TO THIS DECISION

Alexandru LUCINESCU, PhD

Associate professor, National Defense University “Carol I”, Bucharest, Romania
alucinescu@gmail.com

***Abstract:** The aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine included the blockade of Ukrainian ports from the Black Sea which triggered a severe worldwide shortage of agricultural commodities. Under the auspices of the United Nations and with support from Türkiye it was negotiated an agreement, known as the Black Sea Grain Initiative, concluded in July 2022 between Türkiye, Ukraine and the Russian Federation and which made possible for the export of Ukrainian agricultural products to be resumed via the Black Sea. Since July 2022, the agreement was renewed twice and currently it is in force. The Black Sea Grain Initiative drew the attention of experts who put forward various explanations for the participation of the Russian Federation in the agreement, but their opinions differ in terms of both reasons and their degree of relevancy without yet getting them involved in a debate on this issue. The export of Russian agricultural products and fertilizers without any impediment resulting from sanctions imposed on it following aggression against Ukraine and the maintaining of close relations with developing states, mostly from Northern Africa are commonly indicated as rationales behind this decision. This paper contributes to stimulate debate by critically examining these two explanations in terms of their relative importance for the involvement of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative and by providing arguments in support of the prevalence of the latter one. The paper further encourages debate among experts as a result of broadening the second explanation by including under its scope the preoccupation of the Russian Federation for a close cooperation with China and Türkiye.*

***Keywords:** Black Sea Grain Initiative, aggression against Ukraine, Russian Federation, United Nations, sanctions, agricultural commodities, fertilizers.*

Introduction

In the context of the blockade of the Black Sea Ukrainian ports that was imposed by the Russian Federation as part of its aggression against Ukraine and which severely disrupted the international agricultural market, Türkiye, Ukraine and the Russian Federation signed, on 27 July 2022, under the auspices of the United Nations, the *Initiative on the Safe Transportation of Grain and Foodstuffs from Ukrainian Ports* commonly referred to as the Black Sea Grain Initiative (BSGI). Since then, the agreement was renewed twice and, despite numerous difficulties, it is still implemented. Given its relevancy, BSGI attracted worldwide attention and experts put forward various explanations for the decision of the Russian Federation to become and remain part of it. This paper critically examines one of the most frequent such explanations, namely that the Russian Federation aims at removing the impact on its agricultural exports of sanctions imposed to it following the invasion of Ukraine. To this purpose, in the first section of the paper the rationales behind the participation of the Russian Federation in the BSGI, as identified and ranked by experts, are analyzed and systematized. Its second section is concerned with the context in which the Russian blockade was established and with the content of the BSGI and of the memorandum of understanding concluded on 27 July 2022 between the Russian Federation and the Secretariat of the United Nations in view of the latter acting to facilitate the unimpeded export of Russian agricultural commodities. The third section of the paper considers the relevancy of the BSGI by presenting the importance of both Ukraine and the Russian Federation for the international agricultural market, and the last section examines what role the unrestricted access to global agricultural market actually plays for the decision of the Russian Federation to engage in the BSGI.

1. The view of experts on the rationales behind the participation of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative

Experts who consider the BSGI indicate various reasons for the entering of the Russian Federation into this agreement, but they do not all mention the same reasons for this decision or assign to them the same degree of relevancy for it. The existence of different perspectives on this topic has not yet triggered a debate among experts who still do not take into account each other's views so that highlighting the possibility of such a debate could provide the background for a debate on this issue.

Thus, Jakub Olchowski (Olchowski 2022), an expert from the Institute of Central Europe, points out that the Russian Federation uses the agreement as a leverage in matters relevant for its conduct of military operations in Ukraine, such as when it threatened to end its participation in case the UN would send a mission to investigate if the drones it uses are of Iranian origin. He equally identifies a parallel between the evolution of the war and the way the Russian Federation participates in the agreement given that its military setbacks coincide with the delays in the transportation of grains that it inflicted by hindering the ships inspection process established under the agreement, a fact which indicates for Olchowski that the Russian Federation employs the agreement as a „weapon of war”. As other reasons for the participation of the Russian Federation in the agreement, Olchowski indicates the reduction of side effects on its agricultural exports resulting from sanctions targeting it (e.g. the unwillingness of financial institutions and transport companies to do business with Russia and the fact that the Baltic ports were not opened for Russian ships carrying fertilizers intended for Asian market). A supplementary reason is for Olchowski the interest of Vladimir Putin to maintain good relations with Türkiye and thus not to affect the reputation of Erdogan both internally and internationally. It is to be observed that Olchowski does not establish a hierarchy of reasons for the participation of the Russian Federation in BSGI so that no determining reason is singled out. However, the order in which these reasons are introduced could possibly be read as an implicit hierarchy of their importance with the highest one being attributed to the first of these reasons.

Alexandra Prokopenko (Prokopenko 2022) from Carnegie Endowment maintains that there are two reasons which determined the Russian Federation to become part of BSGI, namely the easing of sanctions imposed on it following the invasion of Ukraine and the acute need for Ukrainian grain experienced by states from the Middle East and Northern Africa, especially those ones having close ties with the Russian Federation; according to her, these reasons carry different weight for the Russian Federation with the former being the primary one for it. Prokopenko maintains that the easing of sanctions was pursued by the Russian Federation in order to increase its revenues from grain export, to obtain revenues from exporting fertilizers, to have some assets of its banks unfrozen for processing operations connected to agricultural products, to reduce the food insecurity of its own - as a result of being able to import seeds, agricultural machines and their corresponding spare parts, as well as products for crop protection that it was largely depended on -, and to enable agricultural companies owned by oligarchs close to Vladimir Putin to run their business. As for the secondary reason she indicates that some states from Middle East and Northern Africa having close ties with the Russian Federation (e.g. Türkiye, Egypt, Iran, Saudi Arabia) demanded Putin to allow Ukraine to export grains through the Black Sea, those holding power in some of these states expressing concern that grain shortage could undermine their rule by fuelling upheavals similar to those that took place during the so called Arab Spring.

Cameron Watson (Watson 2022) from Dryad Global indicates as motives for the entering of the Russian Federation into the BSGI the fact that it signed a memorandum with the Secretariat of the United Nations which was supposed to act as a facilitator for Russian exports of fertilizers as well as the fact that the Russian Federation committed itself to prevent Asian and African states from plunging into a severe food crisis. Given that the preoccupation for having complete access to the international agriculture market is the first reason to be mentioned, one could suppose that Watson considers it as the most important incentive for the Russian Federation.

Joseph Glauber, Caitlin Welsh and David Laborde (Glauber, Welsh, Laborde 2022) from the Center for Strategic & International Studies, indicate that the Russian Federation entered the agreement because it intended to use it as a leverage for extracting concession from Western states and also because developing states that kept a neutral position towards the war would be affected by its exit from the agreement and, consequently, could adopt a critical position towards it. Once more is missing an explicit assessment of the relative importance of the reasons underpinning the participation of the Russian Federation in the BSGI so that one could suppose that the order in which they are mentioned implies their degree of relevancy with the effect that the first one is the most relevant one.

In an analysis for the International Crisis Group, Oleg Ignatov, Simon Schlegel, Berkay Mandıracı, Rafael Ch. Duran, Richard Gowan, Olga Olikier and Alissa de Carbonnel (Ignatov, Schlegel, Mandıracı, Duran, Gowan, Olikier de Carbonnel 2022) explain the entering of the Russian Federation into the agreement solely on grounds of the desire for its grains and fertilizers exports not to be hampered by the side effects of the sanctions imposed on it. They ground this interpretation on the fact that the same day the Black Sea Grain Initiative was signed, the Russian Federation and the Secretariat of the United Nations (UN Secretariat) concluded a memorandum providing that the UN Secretariat would act in support of facilitating the export of Russian grains and fertilizers by advocating the elimination of the side effects on the export of these products arising out of sanctions imposed by the United States and the European Union. A similar explanation is put forward by Gregor Novak and Helmut Aust from Just Security (Novak, Aust 2022).

Iwona Wiśniewska, Andrzej Wilk, Sławomir Matuszak and Adam Michalski (Wiśniewska, Wilk, Matuszak, Michalski 2022) from the Center for Eastern Studies consider that what determined the Russian Federation to be part of the Black Sea Grain Initiative was its desire to keep close relations with Turkey and countries from the Global South that needed Ukrainian grain.

It is to be observed that improving the conditions for grain and fertilizers export and maintaining good relations with developing states are most frequently indicated as reasons for Russian Federation being part to BSGI with the former reason being considered by Ignatov, Schlegel, Mandıracı, Duran, Gowan, Olikier and de Carbonnel as the only rationale for that involvement. Not all experts mentioning the first reason also mention the second one, and from those ones who refer to both reasons only Prokopenko and possibly Watson ranks the first of them as the primary one. Less frequent among experts is the concern of the Russian Federation for keeping close relations with Türkiye and for using the BSGI for extracting concession from the Western states.

Taking into account that regaining full access to the global agricultural market is largely considered as a rationale for the participation of the Russian Federation in the BSGI and given that this objective is regarded by some experts as a paramount or exclusive rationale for this decision, the present article aims at considering if the unimpeded export of grains and fertilizers represents for the Russian Federation the main reason for signing and implementing the BSGI. In case the findings do not support this assessment, it will be examined whether maintaining good relations with developing states and/or with Türkiye could play for a more important role in that decision by the Russian Federation.

2. The Black Sea Grain Initiative in context

As soon as the invasion of Ukraine started on 24 February 2022, the Russian forces prevented commercial ships from leaving the ports from the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov, the total number of vessels blocked therein reaching 300 in mid-March (Martin 2022, France 24 2022). The hostile actions of the Russian Federation severely affected the export of cereals produced by Ukraine, given that Ukraine exports them almost entirely (90%) via the Black Sea (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development 2022) and that the creation, proposed by the European Commission in May 2022, of the alternative EU-Ukraine Solidarity Lanes enabling the

land transportation of almost 20 million tonnes of grains was highly challenging (European Commission b 2022). The blockade was effective, as proved by the fact that, as long as it was in force, no vessel carrying agricultural products could leave Ukrainian ports (UN News a 2022), with the result that the quantities of wheat exported by Ukraine in March, April and May 2022 dropped to almost zero compared to the same period of the previous year when they raised above 500 000 tones (Council of the European Union d 2022).

The signing at Istanbul on 22 July 2022 of the *Initiative on the Safe Transportation of Grain and Foodstuffs from Ukrainian Ports*¹, commonly known as the Black Sea Grain Initiative, marked the end of the blockade and the resumption of exports of agricultural products by Ukraine. According to this document, which was agreed upon by the Russian Federation, Ukraine and Türkiye and whose negotiation was actively enabled by the United Nations and Türkiye (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development 2022), the parties will assure a safe route of navigation (maritime humanitarian corridor) for vessels involved in the export of grain, related foodstuffs and fertilizers, the latter one being considered to include ammonia, through the Black Sea Ukrainian ports of Odesa, Chernomorsk, Yuzhny; it is to be remarked that the port of Yuzhny is highly important not only for Ukraine but also for the export of fertilizers by the Russian Federation given that there ends the pipeline whereby ammonia, a gas indispensable for the production of nitrogen fertilizer (ThyssenKrupp 2022), is transported from the Russian Federation (Reuters b 2022). In line with this commitment, no attacks were to be carried out against such vessels or against facilities used in those ports for the export of the mentioned goods. The implementation of the agreement was entrusted to the Joint Coordination Centre headquartered in Istanbul and made-up of representatives of the three signatories and of the United Nations and it involved the inspection, conducted by inspection teams composed of representatives of the parties and of the United Nations, of each vessel in designated Türkiye's ports. The agreement was concluded for an initial period of 120 days, namely until 19 November, but it provided for the possibility of its automatic extension in case all parties agree.

On 1 August the initiative became operational and the first vessel, Razoni, departed from the port of Odesa carrying 26 000 metric tonnes of corn (UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs 2022) and was followed by many others² but on 29 October, that is less than one month before its initial date of expiration, the Russian Federation suspended its participation, accusing Ukrainian forces of using the maritime humanitarian corridor for launching a sustained drone attack on the Russian Black Sea Fleet based in Sevastopol, and made clear that it would continue to implement the agreement only if Ukraine would provide guarantees that it would no more use the humanitarian corridor for attacking Russian forces (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation 2022). The accusation was rejected in strong terms by the Ukrainian minister of foreign affairs, Dmytro Kuleba, who blamed the Russian Federation for deliberately undermining of the agreement (Dmytro Kuleba 2022, Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine 2022). Despite the position of the Russian Federation, the vessels continued to leave the Ukrainian ports³ and eventually the Russian leadership unexpectedly decided to resume on 3 November the implementation of the agreement (Reuters c 2022). The decision was considered hasty because, when the Russian minister of defence announced that the Russian Federation resumed its participation, the Russian state media, including the spokesman of Vladimir Putin, Dmitri Peskov, insisted that the security guarantees on the part of Ukraine failed to be provided so that it was not

¹ Initiative on the Safe Transportation of Grain and Foodstuffs from Ukrainian Ports, 22 July 2022, Istanbul, https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/black_sea_grain_initiative_full_text.pdf.

²The complete list of vessels that operated under the Black Sea Grain Initiative during its first period of implementation is available on the webpage of the Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Initiative (<https://www.un.org/en/black-sea-grain-initiative/vessel-movements>).

³ From 29 October until 02 November, a total number of 22 commercial vessels left the Ukrainian ports carrying agricultural commodities (Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, Vessel movement – Outbound voyages, <https://www.un.org/en/black-sea-grain-initiative/vessel-movements>).

possible for the Russian Federation to implement its obligations under the agreement (Wiśniewska 2022).

Despite all these difficulties, the signatories of the Black Sea Grain Initiative decided in November 2022 to extend it for an additional 120 days (United Nations Türkiye 2022), in March 2023 a decision was taken to extend it for only 60 days (UN News a 2023) and in May 2023 the agreement was again prolonged for an additional 60 days (UN News b 2023).

It is to be mentioned that the same day the Black Sea Grain Initiative was signed, a separate agreement that did not represent a treaty was concluded in Istanbul between the Russian Federation and the Secretariat of the United Nations for the purpose of facilitating access to the global market of Russian food products and of both the Russian fertilizers and the Russian raw materials required for their production⁴. The document provided that the Secretariat had to engage the state and the private sector in order to give effect to the exemption of these Russian goods from the sanctions imposed to it and, also, that it had to endeavour to support the elimination of the logistic, financial and insurance barriers to the export of them arising out of the restrictive measures the Russian Federation was subjected to. It is to be remarked that, under this agreement, the Secretariat was not supposed to advocate the lifting of the sanctions imposed to the Russian Federation but only to use its authority to promote the elimination of their side effects on the Russian export of the mentioned goods, as well as the full implementation of the exceptions regarding these products that have been made part of those sanctions (see on this point Ignatov, Schlegel, Mandıracı, Duran, Gowan, Oliker, de Carbonnel 2022). It was decided that the validity of the agreement would extend for a three-year period a time framework that is far better compared to that of the Black Sea Grain Initiative which has to be renewed every four months. The commitment of the Secretariat of the United Nations to this agreement was expressed by the UN Secretary General, António Guterres, during the first period of its implementation as well as when the agreement was extended⁵.

The Black Sea Grain Initiative is considered to be a success given that, during its first period of implementation, the quantity of grains and corresponding foodstuffs that it made possible to be exported reached 11.1 million tonnes (United Nations Türkiye 2022) and that, until the beginning of December, the quantity exported reached almost 16 million tonnes - maize (45%), wheat (29%), sunflower oil (6%), sunflower meal (6) and other types of grain (14%) (Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Initiative b 2023). Up to the beginning of May 2023, 29,219 million tonnes had been exported as a result of the BSGI, corn and wheat accounting for 77% of all commodities whose export was enabled by this agreement (Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Initiative b 2023).

3. Ukraine and the Russian Federation as prominent players in the global agricultural market

The high relevance of the Black Sea Grain Initiative follows from the prominent role played by Ukraine on the global agricultural market where it is a key exporter in the field of cereals and oilseeds. Thus, back in 2021, Ukraine was the second largest exporter of barley on the global

⁴ *Memorandum of Understanding between the Russian Federation and the Secretariat of the United Nations on promoting Russian food products and fertilizers to the world markets*, 22 July 2022, https://news.un.org/pages/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/MOU_21_July_UN-Secretariat86.pdf

⁵ See, for example Secretary General of the United Nations, Secretary-General's remarks to the Media on the Black Sea Grain Initiative, 01 August 2022, <https://www.un.org/sg/en/content/sg/press-encounter/2022-08-01/secretary-generals-remarks-the-media-the-black-sea-grain-initiative> („Together with the agreed facilitation of the unimpeded access of Russian food products and fertilizers to world markets, it will bring relief and stability to global food markets and help tackle the global food crisis”) and Secretary General of the United Nations, Welcoming Black Sea Grain Initiative's Renewal, Secretary-General Stresses Importance of Diplomacy in Finding Multilateral Solutions, 17 November 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/sgsm21588.doc.htm> („The United Nations is also fully committed to removing the remaining obstacles to exporting food and fertilizers from the Russian Federation. Both agreements signed in Istanbul three months ago are essential to bring down the prices of food and fertilizer and avoid a global food crisis”).

market with 5 611 000 metric tonnes, occupied the third position in the world ranking of maize exporters with 24 676 000 metric tonnes, and was ranked the fifth global exporter of wheat with a total of 20 048 000 metric tonnes (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). Also, in 2021, sunflower oil exports by Ukraine reached 5 135 000 metric tonnes and turned it into the largest global exporter, its exports of rapeseed amounted to 2 660 000 metric tonnes which enabled it to be the third largest exporter worldwide, and, as a result of exporting 164 000 metric tonnes of rape seeds oil, it occupied the seventh position in the global ranking (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2022). The export of agricultural commodities is a very important source of income for Ukraine which back in 2021 exported cereals whose total value amounted to almost \$12 billion (Council of the European Union d 2022) and sunflower oil and rapeseed worth \$ 8,1 billion (Feingold 2022).

Considering the regions and the corresponding states where Ukraine exported cereals in 2021, Pacific Asia received the largest share (30%), with Indonesia (13%) and Philippines (6%) as main beneficiaries, the exports to North Africa reached 27% and have been directed mainly to Egypt (14%), Tunisia (5%) and Morocco (5%), and North-East Asia and South Asia both came the third with 14% each from the total cereals exports, Bangladesh being the country whose imports reached 9% (Council of the European Union d 2022). Southern Africa (7%) and Europe (6%) occupied the last two positions in this ranking, the European Union, with a 5% share, being the most relevant market in Europe (Council of the European Union d 2022). A focus on the 2021 wheat exports by Ukraine highlights the degree in which various states depended on it. Thus, in the regions mentioned above, the situation was as follows: Pacific Asia - Indonesia (over 20%), Thailand (over 10%); North Africa - Libya and Tunisia (each one over 30%), Egypt (over 20%), Morocco (over 10%), Sudan (under 10%); South Asia – Pakistan (over 30%), Bangladesh (over 10%), Iran and Sri Lanka (each one below 10%); Southern Africa – Seychelles (over 90%), Madagascar (over 20%), Tanzania (over 10%), Zambia (10%), Zimbabwe and Democratic Republic of Congo (each one below 10%); Europe – Switzerland, Greece, Albania (each one below 10%), Republic of Moldova (30%) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). According to statistics, in 2021 no state from North-East Asia region imported wheat from Ukraine (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2022). In 2021, apart from the states mentioned above, the dependence on the wheat imported from Ukraine was also present in other African states (Somalia, Eritrea, Djibouti – each one over 40%, Mauritania – 40%, Ethiopia – over 20%, Kenya and Uganda – each one over 10%, Senegal, Nigeria, Gabon, Ghana, Cote d'Ivoire, Cameroon – each one below 10%) and in states from the Middle East (Lebanon – 60%, Oman – 30%, Yemen – over 20%, Saudi Arabia – 20%, Israel and Türkiye – each one over 10%, Jordan – below 10%) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2002). Given that, for the population from North Africa and the Middle East, wheat represents the basic food, the dependency on the wheat imports from Ukraine of the states from these regions is highly relevant for them in terms of food security (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development 2022).

The shortage of grains caused by the blockade imposed by the Russian Federation determined a rapid increase of food prices worldwide, in March 2022 their level being 60% higher than in the same month from 2020, and the ascending trend continued until May 2022, when the EU-Ukraine Solidarity Lanes have been established (Council of the European Union f 2022). The cereals price index for 2022 raised from 145.3 in February to 170.1 in March, reached a pick in May (173.5) and, upon the entry into force of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, its value decreased in July (147.3) and August (145.6) and varied between 147.9 and 150.4 from September to November (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations b 2022).

Summing up, when the blocking of the Ukrainian ports by the Russian Federation started it was expected for it to affect mostly Pacific Asia and North Africa regions, to which more than 50% (57%) of the total cereals exports have been directed to in 2021, and also the countries with a relevant degree of dependence on the wheat imported from Ukraine (minimum 20%), that is, in descending order, Seychelles, Lebanon, Somalia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Mauritania, Libya, Tunisia,

Oman, Egypt, Madagascar, Yemen, Ethiopia, Saudi Arabia; in the latter case, as a result of the high importance of wheat in North Africa and the Middle East, the food security of Libya, Tunisia, Egypt, Lebanon, Oman, Yemen and Saudi Arabia was going to significantly decrease.

Like Ukraine, Russian Federation occupies a prominent position on the global agricultural market being in 2021 the largest exporter of wheat (32 917 000 metric tons), the third most important exporter of barley (5 156 000 metric tons), and the sixth global exporter of maize (3 803 000 metric tons) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). Also in 2021, the Russian Federation was ranked the second exporter of sunflower (3 112 000 metric tons), the fourth largest exporter of rapeseed (277 000 metric tons), and the second larger global exporter of rape seeds oil (802 000 metric tons) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). Equally in 2021, the Russian Federation was the most important global exporter of nitrogen fertilizers and the second larger exporter of potassic fertilisers and of phosphorous fertilisers while Ukraine was not ranked among the first ten global exporters of none of these products (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022).

The dependency of some states on the imports of wheat and fertilizers could be used as a leverage by the Russian Federation in relation with them. As for the dependency on the wheat imported from the Russian Federation, statistics for 2021 provide the following percentages: Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Georgia (90%), Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Democratic Republic of Congo, Finland (over 80%), Benin, Türkiye, Congo (over 60%), Albania, Liberia, Rwanda, Namibia, Eritrea, Senegal (over 50%), Madagascar (50%), Somalia, Cameroon, Nicaragua, Togo, Lithuania, Egypt, United Republic of Tanzania, Burundi (over 40%), Latvia, Sudan, Iran, Burkina Faso (30%), Libya, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Israel, Uganda, Jordan, Malta, Cyprus, Angola, Cote d'Ivoire, Mali, Greece, Malawi (over 20%) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). Taking into account that, as already mentioned, the diet of people from North Africa and the Middle East relies heavily on wheat, it follows that the Russian Federation has the capacity to exert significant influence on Egypt, Libya, Sudan, Türkiye, Saudi Arabia, Israel and Jordan. With respect to the dependency on fertilizers imported from the same state, the figures indicated by statistics covering 2021 are as follows : Mongolia, Belarus (over 90%), Finland, Kazakhstan, Estonia, Republic of Moldova (over 70%), Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan (over 60%), Serbia, Latvia, Honduras (over 50%), Cameroon, Georgia, Peru, Armenia (over 40%), Ghana, Israel, Ecuador, Senegal, Slovenia, Suriname (over 30%), Lithuania, Panama, Mauritania, Benin, Cote d'Ivoire, Costa Rica, Morocco, Congo, China, Poland, Guinea, Mexico, Guatemala, North Macedonia, Ireland, Brazil (over 20%) and Denmark, Sierra Leone (20%) (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations a 2022). It is to be observed that no state from North Africa and, except for Israel, no state from the Middle East, rely on the Russian Federation for satisfying its needs for fertilizers so that the Russian Federation cannot use in relation with states from these regions the export of this product as another leverage alongside its wheat exports.

4. Explaining the participation of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative

Ukraine has as a paramount interest to repeal the Russian aggression and the Black Sea Grain Initiative provides it with revenues in billions of dollars (Prokopenko 2002) which enable it to sustain the war effort. Prior to the entry into force of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, it was estimated for 2022 a 45% contraction of the economy of Ukraine and a \$50 billion deficit of its budget, the blocking of agricultural exports being a significant contributing factor (Ignatov, Schlegel, Mandiraci, Duran, Gowan, Olikier, de Carbonnel 2022). On its side, Türkiye has significant economic and political gains from the implementation of the Black Sea Grain Initiative. Thus, it processes grain from both Ukraine and the Russian Federation in order to make it available worldwide, benefits from a 25% reduction of the contract price for the Ukrainian grain (Soylu 2022) and augments its revenues from ships crossing the straits under that agreement given that, since October 2022, it increased 5 times the fee charged for this operation (Kolishnichenko 2022).

From a political point of view, Türkiye strengthened its international position by positioning itself as a relevant international player as it proved capable to significantly contribute to solving a pressing global problem.

In order to adequately understand the gains for the Russian Federation it is necessary to briefly review the sanctions imposed to it by the European Union and the United States of America in response of its aggression against Ukraine. Both international actors imposed sanctions against the Russian Federation but their officials argued that these ones did not target Russian agricultural exports so that they did not prevent the Russian Federation to export on the agricultural global market or to operate the corresponding transactions (Council of the European Union b 2023, Department of the Treasury 2022). Thus, until February 2023, the European Union adopted tenth packages of sanctions (Council of the European Union c 2023) of which only the ban on vessels operating under the Russian flag to have access to ports belonging to EU member states, a sanction included in the fifth package that was adopted on 8 April, was considered to compromise the agricultural exports of the Russian Federation and therefore the vessels carrying agricultural and food products have been excluded from its scope (Council of the European Union b 2022)⁶. Some sanctions put in place by the European Union target the banking sector of the Russian Federation as it is the case with the exclusion of important Russian banks from SWIFT - a restrictive measure that was introduced through the third package of sanctions adopted on 2 March 2022 (Council of the European Union a 2022) and which have been extended over the Russian Agricultural Bank in June when the sixth package of sanctions was agreed upon (Council of the European Union c 2022) -, and with the freezing of their assets which was included in the fifth package of sanctions adopted in April (Council of the European Union b 2022, European Commission a 2022). However, in anticipation of the signing of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, the European Union decided in July to unfreeze assets of top Russian banks in order to enable execution of transactions with agricultural products (Reuters a 2022, Ignatov, Schlegel, Mandıracı, Duran, Gowan, Oliker, de Carbonnel 2022). As for the United States, albeit it imposed severe sanctions on the Russian Federation (S&P Global 2022), including on some of its financial institutions whose assets have been frozen or, as in the case of the Russian Agricultural Bank, subjected to other types of restrictions, it neither banned the selling to the Russian Federation of agricultural equipment and associated spare parts, nor it prohibited the import from this state of agricultural products, fertilizers being included under this category (Radio France International 2022, Department of the Treasury 2022, White House 2022, US Department of State 2022). Prior to the signing of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, on 14 July, the United States introduced a series of exceptions to the restrictions imposed to the transactions concerning the Russian Federation, allowing those ones for agricultural commodities and agricultural equipment (Office of Foreign Assets Control of the Department of the Treasury 2022).

As previously mentioned, the rationale that for many experts seems obvious for the participation of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative is the interest for its agricultural exports not to be subjected, in a direct or indirect manner, to sanctions imposed to it. Under this explanation, the Russian Federation considered that its revenues from agricultural exports would be substantially higher as a result of it being part to this agreement and, consequently, to the subsequent memorandum of understanding concluded with the Secretariat of the United Nations than if it have refused to be involved in it. Moreover, it is equally justified to consider that the Russian Federation estimated that the significant financial benefits obtained by

⁶See also Council Decision (CFSP) 2022/578 of 8 April 2022 amending Decision 2014/512/CFSP concerning restrictive measures in view of Russia's actions destabilising the situation in Ukraine Article 4ha 5 (b), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3A0J.L_2022.111.01.0070.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AL%3A2022%3A111%3ATOC. According to this decision of the Council of the European Union „By way of derogation from paragraph 1, the competent authorities may authorise a vessel to access a port, under such conditions as they deem appropriate, after having determined that the access is necessary for (...) the purchase, import or transport of pharmaceutical, medical, agricultural and food products, including wheat and fertilisers whose import, purchase and transport is allowed under this Decision”.

Ukraine under the terms of the Black Sea Grain Initiative would be less important than the revenues it could obtain in return to its involvement in it. In other words, the Russian Federation traded off the lifting of the blockade of three Ukrainian ports for unimpeded export of its agricultural commodities, including fertilizers and raw materials required for their production, particularly ammonia.

It is to be observed that the sanctions imposed to the Russian Federation by the European Union and the United States, as indicated above, never targeted the export of agricultural products but exempted it from the beginning so that one cannot rightly speak about them as directly affecting this sector and thus about the Russian Federation being driven by the concern for its agricultural commodities not to be directly affected by these sanctions.

As for the elimination of indirect consequences on Russian agricultural exports of international financial sanctions, it could be considered as an objective followed by the Russian Federation by means of signing the Black Sea Grain Initiative, but the viability of this rationale has to be assessed in connection with the fact that, since the start of the implementation of this agreement, Russian officials complain that the export of agricultural products and fertilizers by the Russian Federation continued to be hampered by the international sanctioned. Thus, prior to the extension of the agreement, the Russian authorities maintained that the financial obstacles for the transactions involving Russian agricultural products, such as their inclusion into SWIFT system, were yet to be eliminated (TASS 2022, Reuters d 2022). Also, before the second renewal of the BSGI, which, because of the opposition on the Russian side, was 60 days shorter than the first one, the Russian foreign minister, Sergei Lavrov, warned that the extension of the agreement was imperiled by the fact that only half of the commitments to lift barriers to the agricultural commodities exported by his country had been respected (Reuters a 2022, Davis 2023). In April 2023, in anticipation of the negotiations for prolonging the BSGI beyond May 2023, Lavrov stated that the BSGI failed to satisfy Russian demands for unimpeded export of its agricultural commodities and fertilizers so that its further renewal is useless for the Russian Federation (Massoud 2023).

It could be concluded that, according to the Russian officials, during the implementation of the BSGI the international sanctions continued to hamper the Russian export of agricultural products, a shortfall which, if real, would be detrimental to its agricultural exports and would reduce its associated revenues. Also, if the sanctions imposed to the Russian Federation by the European Union and the United States and which they have eased prior to the signing of the Black Sea Grain Initiative provide a conducive environment for the Russian agricultural exports, their volume and ensuing revenues should not be affected. However, according to Russian data, the export of agricultural products by the Russian Federation in 2022 increased with 12% compared with the last year and generated revenues estimated at \$40 billion, a value that was \$2.9 billion higher than in 2021; in case of grains, the export increased with 14% (Meatcommerce 2022)⁷, the record value of their export being also acknowledged by international experts (Devitt 2022). These statistics prove that either the sanctions by the European Union and the United States, albeit affecting the Russian agricultural export, had a minor impact on it, or that these sanctions were adequately designed not to impede the agricultural exports by the Russian Federation, in both cases the implication being the same one: the sanctions did not play a prominent role in the decision of the Russian Federation to join the Black Sea Grain Initiative. Moreover, if the participation of the Russian Federation in BSGI really failed to meet its expectations, it is difficult to understand why it continued to be part of it for almost one year.

As for the comparative financial gains from agricultural exports by the Russian Federation and Ukraine, statistics show that in 2022, compared to Ukraine, the Russian Federation gained almost double from this activity. Thus, according to Russian data, the export of agricultural products by the Russian Federation in 2022 generated revenues estimated at \$40 billion, a value that was \$2.9 billion higher than in 2021; in case of grains, the export increased with 14%

⁷ The data have been presented by the minister of agriculture of the Russian Federation and his deputy.

(Meatcommerce 2022)⁸. The Ukrainian experts indicate that the revenues obtained by Ukraine from exporting agricultural products amount to approximately \$24 billion, a value which is almost 16% lower compared to 2021 (Interfax 2022, Kutchner 2022). Consequently, the Russian Federation gained far more than Ukraine so that, from a financial point of view, the participation of the former in the Black Sea Grain Initiative could be said to be justified. However, as argued above, the Russian agricultural exports in 2022 did not decisively depend on its participation in this agreement so that the main rationale for the willingness of the Russian Federation to allow for Ukraine to obtain even half of its revenues should be looked for somewhere else.

Another plausible reason for the participation of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative is its interest to enable states that it is closely connected with to have access to Ukrainian grains, taking into account that the Russian exports could not satisfy their needs. For example, China, between 2018-2021, increased up to five times the quantity of grain imported from Ukraine so that 20,7% from the total grain export by Ukraine in 2021 have been directed to China (UkrAgroConsult 2022). Egypt was in 2021 the second important market for Ukrainian grains with \$1.386 billion total value of imports, a figure which was bigger compared with the one from the preceding year (UkrAgroConsult 2022). In a document from 03 May 2022 submitted to the World Bank, Egypt indicated that this state was the world largest importer of wheat, that the wheat it imported satisfied over 60% of its domestic demand and originated in proportion of 20-25% (around 2,4 - 3 million metric tonnes) from Ukraine, so that the unavailability of this Ukrainian commodity as a result of the war was undermining its economy (Gomaa 2022)⁹. Therefore, the Egyptian minister of supply and internal trade, Ali al-Moselhi, publicly expressed his satisfaction for the signing of the Black Sea Grain Initiative (Gomaa 2022). Also in 2021, the third largest importer of Ukrainian grain was Türkiye with \$918 million (UkrAgroConsult 2022). The following positions in 2021 top 10 importers of Ukrainian grain have been occupied, in order, by Indonesia - \$750 million, Spain - \$645 million, the Netherlands - \$552 million, Iran - \$533 million, Pakistan - \$355 million, Libya - \$342 million, Tunisia - \$306 million (UkrAgroConsult 2022). Apart from Egypt, back in 2021 many other African states depended on the wheat imported from Ukraine, their number representing 23 out of 41 states that imported this commodity from there. More exactly, the dependency of Seychelles was almost complete (over 90%), it overpassed 40% in case of four states (Somalia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Mauritania, Ethiopia), it went beyond 30% for other two states (Libya, Tunisia), it exceeded 20% with respect to two states (Madagascar, Ethiopia), it surpassed 10% for five states (Maroc, Tanzania, Zambia, Kenya, Uganda), and, finally, it was less than 10 in the case of four states (Sudan, Zimbabwe, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Senegal, Nigeria, Gabon, Ghana). Taking Egypt into account and excluding Seychelles it follows that the states most dependent on Ukrainian wheat are mainly located in two regions: Northern Africa and the Horn of Africa.

The Russian Federation has developed significant ties with China, Türkiye, Egypt and many African states which, since the war in Ukraine outbroke, prompted them to adopt an opened attitude towards it.

Considering the relations between the Russian Federation and China, it is to be observed that weeks before the start of the Russian invasion, on 4 February, China and the Russian Federation agreed on *Russia-China Joint Statement on International Relations*, a landmark document which imposed no limits to the partnership between the two countries and whereby they committed to mutually support their vital interest¹⁰. As the war in Ukraine unfolded, China did not condemn Russian military actions, did not imposed sanctions to it but criticised those states that did so, supported the Russian Federation within the United Nations and in other international fora, and joined the Russian Federation in military exercises. The day the invasion begun, the Chinese

⁸ The data have been presented by the minister of agriculture of the Russian Federation and his deputy.

⁹ The World Bank, Emergency Food Security and Resilience Support Program, Project Information Document (PID), 03 May 2022.

¹⁰ Russia-China Joint Statement On International Relations, February 4, 2022, <https://china.usc.edu/russia-china-joint-statement-international-relations-february-4-2022>.

Ministry of Foreign Affairs spokesperson referred to the military actions of the Russian Federation as a special military operation, a term used by the Russian officials to designate their actions, while the Chinese minister of foreign affairs emphasised in a phone call with his Russian counterpart that the security concerns of the Russian Federation were legitimate ones (U.S.- China Economic and Security Review Commission 2022). A few days later, on 28 February, in the context of sanctions targeting the Russian Federation, the Chinese minister of foreign affairs stated that China would continue its normal trade relation with this state and that the unilateral sanctions are contrary to international law (Zhen 2022). Also, on 25 February, China abstained when a resolution by the UN Security Council condemning the Russian Federation for conducting an aggression against Ukraine¹¹ was put to the vote, arguing that Ukraine had turned into „an outpost for confrontation between major powers” and insisting that the security concerns of the Russian Federation were legitimate but were not adequately addressed¹². In case of all resolutions adopted in 2022 at the 11th emergency special session of the UN General Assembly and which condemned the actions of Russian Federation (Resolution ES-11/1. *Aggression against Ukraine*, Resolution ES-11/2 *Humanitarian consequences of the aggression against Ukraine*, Resolution ES-11/3 *Suspension of the rights of membership of the Russian Federation in the Human Rights Council*, Resolution ES-11/4 *Territorial integrity of Ukraine: defending the principles of the Charter of the United Nations*)¹³ China constantly abstained¹⁴; thus, when Resolution ES-11/1 was adopted, China maintained that this document underestimated the relevancy of the principle of indivisible security (U.S.- China Economic and Security Review Commission 2022). Later on, China joined the Russian Federation in opposing the use in the *G20 Bali Leaders` Declaration* from 15 November of the term war for qualifying the situation in Ukraine (U.S.- China Economic and Security Review Commission 2022). It is also relevant that China and the Russian Federation participated in a common military exercise on 24 May 2022, an opportunity for the Chinese foreign ministry spokesperson to underline the „importance and resilience” of the relationship between China and the Russian Federation (U.S.- China Economic and Security Review Commission 2022), between 1-7 September, China equally took part in the Russian led Vostok-2022 strategic command post exercise (President of Russia 2022), and in December the two countries have been involved in joint naval exercise in East China Sea (Associated Press 2022). Recently, in March 2023, the Chinese president Xi Jinping met Vladimir Putin in Moscow in what represented his first visit abroad after being re-elected in this position (McCarthy 2023).

Focusing on the relations between the Russian Federation and Egypt, it is to be observed that in October 2018 the two countries signed the Agreement on Comprehensive Partnership and Strategic Cooperation covering military, economic and trade aspects (President of Russia 2019), a document which came shortly after the conclusion of a multi-billion agreement related to the creation of a Russian Industrial Zone close to the Suez Canal (Shay 2018). It is equally highly relevant for the relations between Russia and Egypt the fact that in 2022 the Russian Federation started the construction of the first two units of the first ever Egyptian nuclear plant (World Nuclear

¹¹ UN Security Council, Draft Resolution S/2022/155, operational paragraph 2, 25 February 2022, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N22/271/07/PDF/N2227107.pdf?OpenElement>

¹² UN Security Council, Record of the 8979th meeting, p. 12, S/PV.8979, 25 February 2022, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N22/269/25/PDF/N2226925.pdf?OpenElement>.

¹³ UN General Assembly, Eleventh Emergency Special Session, 28 February – 2 March 2022, 23-24 March 2022, 7 April 2022, 10-12 October 2022, <https://www.un.org/en/ga/sessions/emergency11th.shtml>.

¹⁴ United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, General Assembly Overwhelmingly Adopts Resolution Demanding Russian Federation Immediately End Illegal Use of Force in Ukraine, Withdraw All Troops, 02 March 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12407.doc.htm>; United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, General Assembly Adopts Text Recognizing Scale of Humanitarian Woes Arising from Russian Federation’s Ukraine Offensive as Unseen in Many Decades, 24 March 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12411.doc.htm>; United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, General Assembly Adopts Text to Suspend Russian Federation from Human Rights Council, Continuing Emergency Special Session on Humanitarian Crisis in Ukraine, 7 April 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12414.doc.htm>; United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, With 143 Votes in Favour, 5 Against, General Assembly Adopts Resolution Condemning Russian Federation’s Annexation of Four Eastern Ukraine Regions, 12 October 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12458.doc.htm>.

News 2002). These solid ties with the Russian Federation prompted the Egyptian president to be reluctant to condemn the aggression against Ukraine when it started and only the mounting pressure on the part of G7 and EU member states made Egypt support the adoption by the UN General Assembly on 2 of March 2022 of Resolution ES-11 (US Embassy in Egypt 2022); latter on, Egypt voted for un General Assembly Resolutions ES-11/2 and ES-11/4, but abstained in case of Resolution ES-11/3 which suspended the Russian Federation from the Human Rights Council¹⁵. However, Egypt did not sanction the Russian Federation and, in June 2022, its president attended an economic forum held in St. Petersburg where he called the relationships of his country with Russia as being distinguished ones (Amin 2022).

As for Türkiye, under the leadership of Recep Erdogan, it assumed as an important foreign policy objective the development of relationship with Ukraine for keeping the Russian Federation in balance and thus, for preventing it from dominating in the Black Sea region (Atlantic Council 2022). It could be mentioned that, prior to the war, in 2020, Türkiye and Ukraine concluded military agreements designed to support the development of cooperation in the field of defence industry and to provide a framework for common military initiatives (Independent 2020, Associated Press 2020). Equally, Türkiye supplied Ukraine with Bayraktar drones that proved essential in countering the initial Russian advance into its territory. On the other side, Türkiye does not want for the Russian Federation to collapse fearing that this would generate a power void affecting its interests in South Caucasus and the Middle East (Kusa 2022). Moreover, Türkiye has important economic ties with the Russian Federation, which represents for it a relevant trading partner (\$32,5 billion in 2021) (Kusa 2022) and a very important energy supplier, providing it with 50% of its demand for natural gas, the second largest demand after that of Germany (Kirişci 2022, Pearson 2022), and equally depends on the Russian Federation for countering the Kurdish military groups from Syria (Cook 2022) and for keeping areas in northeast Syria outside the control of the Assad regime and thus as a returning place for many Syrian refugees currently based in Türkiye (Atlantic Council 2022). Since the beginning of war, many Turkish companies entered the Russian market to replace Western companies that left the country and Russian tourists and capital have been attracted to Türkiye (Tharoor 2022). As the war unfolded, on 5 August 2022, Putin and Erdogan met in Sochi and agreed to accelerate the economic cooperation, particularly in the areas of transport, agriculture, construction industries and finance. Unlike the European Union and the United States, Türkiye did not impose sanctions against the Russian Federation (Kusa 2022) but within the United Nations it provided support for Ukraine by sponsoring the UN Security Council draft resolution S/2022/155 and attending the meeting in which the document was rejected as a result of the veto expressed by the Russian Federation¹⁶ and by voting in favor of all resolutions adopted in 2022 at the 11th emergency special session of the UN General Assembly¹⁷; in case of the first of these resolutions, Resolution ES-11/1, it presented itself as a friend of both parties

¹⁵ United Nations, General Assembly Adopts Text Recognizing Scale of Humanitarian Woes Arising from Russian Federation's Ukraine Offensive as Unseen in Many Decades, 24 March 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12411.doc.htm>. United Nations, General Assembly Adopts Text to Suspend Russian Federation from Human Rights Council, Continuing Emergency Special Session on Humanitarian Crisis in Ukraine, 7 April 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12414.doc.htm>. United Nations, With 143 Votes in Favour, 5 Against, General Assembly Adopts Resolution Condemning Russian Federation's Annexation of Four Eastern Ukraine Regions, 12 October 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12458.doc.htm>

¹⁶UN Security Council, Record of the 8979th meeting, p. 2, S/PV.8979, 25 February 2022.

¹⁷ United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, General Assembly Overwhelmingly Adopts Resolution Demanding Russian Federation Immediately End Illegal Use of Force in Ukraine, Withdraw All Troops, 02 March 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12407.doc.htm>. United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, Speakers Discuss Two Competing Draft Resolutions on Humanitarian Situation in Ukraine, as General Assembly Resumes Emergency Special Session, 23 March 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12410.doc.htm>. United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, UN General Assembly votes to suspend Russia from the Human Rights Council, 7 April 2022, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/04/1115782>. United Nations, Meetings Coverage and Press Releases, With 143 Votes in Favour, 5 Against, General Assembly Adopts Resolution Condemning Russian Federation's Annexation of Four Eastern Ukraine Regions, 12 October 2022, <https://press.un.org/en/2022/ga12458.doc.htm>

engaged in the conflict and offering to facilitate its peaceful resolution. Consequently, Türkiye avoided to take sides in the war and, choosing the middle ground, it positioned itself as an enabler for the negotiations between belligerents, including for the Black Sea Grain Initiative, a role by which it justified its decision not to follow the hard stance adopted by Western states towards the Russian Federation.

The Russian interests in Africa and, in particular, in North Africa and in the Horn of Africa, Africa representing for the Russian Federation a key foreign policy objective that it already has and that it will constantly and actively pursue (Siegle 2022). A landmark event for the Russian strategy towards Africa was the first Russia-Africa Summit held in 2019 at Sochi and which brought together high-level representatives of around 50 African states¹⁸; a second such summit is planned for July 2023¹⁹. The 2019 summit was co-hosted by the Russian Federation and Egypt, whose president was the incumbent Chairperson of the African Union and led to the adoption of a declaration which stressed the „convergence or similarity of approaches to many issues on the global and regional agendas”²⁰. The close ties between the Russian Federation and the African Union manifested also during the war in Ukraine when, prior to the signing of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, the chairperson of the African Union, Macky Sall, addressed the 30-31 May extraordinary European Council expressing the view that African states were affected by the negative impact that sanctions imposed to the Russian Banks had on the export of cereals and fertilizers by the Russian Federation (The Guardian 2022), an assertion that he repeated on the occasion of his meeting on 3 June 2022 with Vladimir Putin (President of Russia 2022). Speaking to the European leaders, Sall equally underlined the strong reliance of African states on wheat imported from Ukraine and pleaded for finding rapid solutions for making it available to them.

As for Libya, Egypt and the Russian Federation both provide support for field marshal Khalifa Haftar, the former having actively supported him during the second civil war by means of the Wagner Group and pursuing the objective of consolidating its influence in the country in order to project power in the wider region (Wehrey 2022). In the Horn of Africa, the Russian Federation renewed under Putin’s leadership its quest for relevancy that it had lost after the demise of the Soviet Union, thus competing with China, United States and some major European powers (Generoso 2022).

An analysis of the results obtained under the Black Sea Grain Initiative until 13 May 2023 show that China and Türkiye occupy the first (7 million metric tonnes) and the third position (3,1 million metric tonnes) respectively in the ranking of beneficiaries of the grain exported by Ukraine in the framework of the Black Sea Grain Initiative (Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Grain Initiative a 2023). Egypt was ranked sixth position in this top albeit the quantity of grain it received (1,3 million metric tonnes) represented only around half of what Ukraine exported to this country in 2021 (Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Grain Initiative 2023)²¹. As for the African states, the quantities of grains they received under this agreement are the following ones: Djibouti – 6700 metric tonnes, Ethiopia- 1,3 million metric tonnes, Kenia – 376900 metric tonnes, Libya – 558600 metric tonnes, Morocco- 91400 metric tonnes, Somalia – 53500 metric tonnes, Sudan – 65300 metric tonnes, Tunisia – 686500 metric tonnes. The fact that, in September 2022,

¹⁸ Russia-Africa Summit and Economic Forum, <https://summitafrica.ru/en/about-summit/>

¹⁹ Russia—Africa Summit and Economic Forum, July 2023, <https://summitafrica.ru/en/>

²⁰ Declaration of the First Russia–Africa Summit, Sochi, 24 October 2019, <https://summitafrica.ru/en/about-summit/declaration/>.

²¹The relevance for Egypt of the quantity of wheat it imported from Ukraine as a result of the implementation of the Black Sea Grain Initiative has to be assessed in conjunction with the deal concluded by Egypt prior to the signing of that agreement, in June 2022, with four countries (France, Romania, Russian Federation, Bulgaria) for buying 815 000 tonnes of wheat, a move which decreased its dependency on Ukraine and, consequently, gives more relevance to the 657.300 tonnes of wheat that reached Egypt coming from Ukraine.(On the agreement between Egypt and the four mentioned states see Mohammed Hamid, *Egypt carries out its largest wheat purchase since 2012. "Supply Commodities" contracted to buy 815 thousand tons. Agricultural research: a good step and we import 50% from abroad. Abu Saddam: A significant increase in local production this season*, 03. July. 2022, <https://www.albawabhnews.com/4608392>).

Vladimir Putin criticised the agreement on grounds that poor states, including those from Africa, have not really benefited from it (Gijs 2022)²² proves that he intended to use the agreement as a mean to retain and gain influence over them. However, according to statistics, as of 15 March 2023, 65% of the wheat exported by Ukraine under the Black Sea Grain Initiative reached developing countries (Council of the European Union a 2023).

It follows that one could argue that there are reasons to consider that the support provided to developing countries but also to Türkiye and China equally played an important part in the decision of the Russian Federation to sign and implement the BSGI. With respect to Türkiye, it is to be observed that the success of the agreement consolidates its international position and enables it to justify for Western states its policy of not sanctioning the Russian Federation and maintaining close relations with it. As for China, its relevancy for explaining the participation of the Russian Federation in the BSGI, unlike the relevancy of Türkiye for it, was not indicated by the experts whose opinions have been considered in the first section of the paper so that adding the preoccupation for maintaining close relations with China as a rationale for its participation in this agreement facilitates a better understanding of this foreign policy decision.

Conclusions

The participation of the Russian Federation in the Black Sea Grain Initiative is differently explained by experts, but these various opinions still have not reached the level of a debate on this topic. In order to stimulate reflection and exchange of views, the most frequent rationales given for this approach followed by the Russian Federation had been considered, namely the complete exclusion from the effects of sanctions imposed to the Russian Federation of the agricultural commodities and fertilizers exported by it and the desire to maintain close relations with developing states largely dependent on Ukrainian agricultural exports. By comparatively examining the volume and value of Russian agricultural exports from 2021 and 2022 as well as the value of Russian and Ukrainian agricultural exports in 2022 and by considering the constant criticism voiced by Russian officials with respect to ensuring unimpeded access to international agricultural market for Russian commodities, it could be questioned that removing obstacles to Russian agricultural exports represents the primary rationale for the Russian Federation taking part in the Black Sea Grain Initiative. On grounds of the good relationships existing between the Russian Federation and China, Turkey, Egypt, Libya and other African states and taking into account the benefits that these states have as a result of the implementation of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, it is possible to advance the hypothesis that maintaining a favourable attitude on their part towards the Russian Federation is more important for Russian officials than their concern for the effect of sanctions on its access to agricultural global market. Given that consolidating the cooperation with China was not indicated by experts as a relevant reason for the Russian Federation becoming part of the Black Sea Grain Initiative, exposing this incentive helps clarifying the rationales behind this decision.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. *** "Declaration of the First Russia–Africa Summit.", Sochi, 24 October 2019, <https://summitafrica.ru/en/about-summit/declaration/>, accessed November 12, 2022.
2. *** "Initiative on the Safe Transportation of Grain and Foodstuffs from Ukrainian Ports.", 22 July 2022, Istanbul, https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/black_sea_grain_initiative_full_text.pdf, accessed November 22, 2022.

²² Camille Gijs, *Putin threatens to limit Ukraine's Black Sea grain exports*, 7 September 2022, <https://www.politico.eu/article/putin-threat-limit-black-sea-grain-export-ukraine/>

3. *** "Memorandum of Understanding between the Russian Federation and the Secretariat of the United Nations promoting Russian food products and fertilizers to the world markets." 2022, 22. 07. 2022, https://news.un.org/pages/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/MOU_21_July_UN-Secretariat86.pdf, accessed December 06, 2022.
4. *** "Russia-China Joint Statement On International Relations." 2022, 04. 02. 2022, <https://china.usc.edu/russia-china-joint-statement-international-relations-february-4-2022>, accessed April 04, 2023.
5. Amin, Shahira. 2022. "Egypt is cozying up to Russia. It's time for the US to step in." 28. 06. 2022. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/menasource/egypt-is-cozying-up-to-russia-its-time-for-the-us-to-step-in/>, accessed February 10, 2023.
6. Associated Press. 2022. "Turkey, Ukraine Sign Military Cooperation Agreements." 16. 10. 2020, https://www.voanews.com/a/europe_turkey-ukraine-sign-military-cooperation-agreements/6197240.html, accessed January 11, 2023
7. Associated Press. 2022. "Russia and China hold joint naval drills." 22. 12. 2022, https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/russia-and-china-hold-joint-naval-drills/2022/12/22/62d0a5b6-8209-11ed-8738-ed7217de2775_story.html, accessed January 14, 2023.
8. Atlantic Council. 2022. "How long can Turkey play both sides in the Ukraine war? ". 18. 08. 2022, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/how-long-can-turkey-play-both-sides-in-the-ukraine-war/>, accessed December 17, 2022.
9. Cook, Steven A. 2022. "Where Turkey Stands on the Russia-Ukraine War." 03. 03. 2022, <https://www.cfr.org/in-brief/where-turkey-stands-russia-ukraine-war>, accessed November 12, 2022.
10. Council of the European Union. 2022a. "Russia's military aggression against Ukraine: EU bans certain Russian banks from SWIFT system and introduces further restrictions." 02. 03. 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/03/02/russia-s-military-aggression-against-ukraine-eu-bans-certain-russian-banks-from-swift-system-and-introduces-further-restrictions/>, accessed January 11, 2023.
11. Council of the European Union. 2022b. "EU adopts fifth round of sanctions against Russia over its military aggression against Ukraine." 08. 04. 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/04/08/eu-adopts-fifth-round-of-sanctions-against-russia-over-its-military-aggression-against-ukraine/>, accessed January 11, 2023.
12. Council of the European Union. 2022c. "Russia's aggression against Ukraine: EU adopts sixth package of sanctions." 03. 06. 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/03/russia-s-aggression-against-ukraine-eu-adopts-sixth-package-of-sanctions/>, accessed December 11, 2022.
13. Council of the European Union. 2022d. "Infographic - How the Russian invasion of Ukraine has further aggravated the global food crisis." 02. 12. 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/how-the-russian-invasion-of-ukraine-has-further-aggravated-the-global-food-crisis/>, accessed December 15, 2022.
14. Council of the European Union. 2022e. "Food security and affordability." 15. 12. 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/food-security-and-affordability/>, accessed December 29, 2022.
15. Council of the European Union. 2023a. "Infographic - Ukrainian grain exports explained." 20. 01. 2023, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/ukrainian-grain-exports-explained/>, accessed February 10, 2023.
16. Council of the European Union. 2023b. "EU sanctions against Russia explained." 14. 04. 2023, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/sanctions/restrictive-measures-against-russia-over-ukraine/sanctions-against-russia-explained/>, accessed May 11, 2023.
17. Council of the European Union. 2023c. "Timeline - EU response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine." 25. 04. 2023, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/eu-response-ukraine-invasion/timeline-eu-response-ukraine-invasion/>, accessed May 11, 2023.

18. Davis, Caleb. 2023. "Russia raises doubts about grain deal renewal as deadline looms.". 09. 03. 2023, <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/russia-raises-doubts-about-grain-deal-renewal-deadline-looms-2023-03-09/>, accessed April 24, 2023.
19. Devitt, Polina. 2022. "Russia's December wheat exports close to record, experts say.". 03. 12. 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/russias-december-wheat-exports-close-record-experts-say-2022-12-07/#:~:text=It%20estimates%20Russia%27s%20total%202022%2F23%20grain%20exports%20at,pace%20after%20a%20sluggish%20start%20to%20the%20season,> accessed April 24, 2023.
20. Department of the Treasury. 2022. "OFAC Food Security Fact Sheet: Russia Sanctions and Agricultural Trade.". 14. 07. 2022, <https://ofac.treasury.gov/media/924341/download?inline,> accessed December 19, 2022.
21. European Commission. 2022a. "Ukraine: EU agrees fifth package of restrictive measures against Russia.". 08. 04. 2022, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_2332, accessed December 11, 2022.
22. European Commission. 2022b. "European Commission to establish Solidarity Lanes to help Ukraine export agricultural goods.", 12. 05. 2022, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/news/european-commission-establish-solidarity-lanes-help-ukraine-export-agricultural-goods-2022-05-12_en, accessed December 19, 2022.
23. Feingold, Spencer. 2022. "Ukraine's food exports by the numbers.". 25. 07. 2022, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/07/ukraine-s-food-exports-by-the-numbers/,> accessed November 09, 2022.
24. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. 2022a. "Information Note. The importance of Ukraine and the Russian Federation for global agricultural markets and the risks associated with the current conflict.". 25. 03. 2022, <https://www.fao.org/3/cb9236en/cb9236en.pdf,> accessed December 09, 2022.
25. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. 2022b. "World Food Situation." 02. 12. 2022, <https://www.fao.org/worldfoodsituation/foodpricesindex/en/,> accessed December 29, 2022.
26. France 24. 2022. "Russian blockade of Ukraine's ports puts global food supply at risk.". 12. 05. 2022, <https://www.france24.com/en/europe/20220512-russian-blockade-of-ukraine-s-ports-puts-global-food-supply-at-risk,> accessed December 12, 2022.
27. Generoso, Francesco. 2022. "Russian interests in the Horn of Africa: A Red Sea foothold?.", *South African Journal of International Affairs*, vol. 29, no. 4, , pp. 549-570.
28. Gijs, Camille. 2022. "Putin threatens to limit Ukraine's Black Sea grain exports.". 07. 09. 2022, <https://www.politico.eu/article/putin-threat-limit-black-sea-grain-export-ukraine/,> accessed January 15, 2023.
29. Glauber, Joseph. Welsh, Caitlin. Laborde, David. 2022. "Russia's UN Grain Deal Boomerang: Implications for the Deal and Global Food Prices.". 04.11.2022, <https://www.csis.org/analysis/russias-un-grain-deal-boomerang-implications-deal-and-global-food-prices,> accessed January 10, 2023.
30. Goma, Ahmed. 2022. "Egypt pins hopes on Russia-Ukraine grain agreement.". 07. 08. 2022, <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/08/egypt-pins-hopes-russia-ukraine-grain-agreement,> accessed January 24, 2023.
31. Guradian. 2022. "Africa warns of food crisis due to Russian blockade of Ukraine's ports.", 31. 05. 2022, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2022/may/31/africa-warns-of-food-crisis-due-to-russian-blockade-of-ukraines-ports,> accessed January 15, 2023.
32. Ignatov, Oleg. Schlegel, Simon. Mandiracı, Berkay. Duran, Rafael Ch. Gowan, Richard. Oliker, Olga de Carbonnel, Alissa. 2022. "Who are the Winners in the Black Sea Grain Deal?". 03. 08. 2022, <https://www.crisisgroup.org/europe-central-asia/eastern-europe/ukraine/who-are-winners-black-sea-grain-deal,> accessed January 05, 2023.

33. Independent. 2020. "Turkey, Ukraine sign military cooperation agreements.", 16. 10. 2020, <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/turkey-ukraine-sign-military-cooperation-agreements-turkey-volodymyr-zelenskiy-ukraine-russia-dominance-b1080131.html>, accessed December 17, 2022.
34. Interfax. 2022. "Ukraine's revenues from agricultural exports down 16% to \$23.3 bln in 2022 – association.". 27. 12. 2022, https://interfax.com/newsroom/top_stories/86528, accessed January 04, 2023.
35. Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Grain Initiative. 2022. "Cargo destinations.". <https://www.un.org/en/black-sea-grain-initiative/vessel-movements>, accessed January 15, 2023.
36. Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Initiative. 2023a. "Vessel Movements.". <https://www.un.org/en/black-sea-grain-initiative/vessel-movements>, accessed May 27, 2023.
37. Joint Coordination Centre of the Black Sea Initiative. 2023b. "What has been shipped?" <https://www.un.org/en/black-sea-grain-initiative/vessel-movements>, accessed May 16, 2023.
38. Kirişci, Kemal. 2022. "Erdoğan's straits of indecision in the Russia-Ukraine war.". 28. 02. 2022, <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/order-from-chaos/2022/02/28/erdogans-straits-of-indecision-in-the-russia-ukraine-war/>, accessed December 17, 2022.
39. Kolisnichenko, Vadim. 2022. "Turkey has increased the price for passage through the Bosphorus and Dardanelles by 5 times since October." 29 August 2022, <https://gmk.center/en/news/turkey-has-increased-the-price-for-passage-through-the-bosphorus-and-dardanelles-by-5-times-since-october/>, accessed November 22, 2022.
40. Kuleba, Dmytro. 2022. https://twitter.com/DmytroKuleba/status/1586378441548759042?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw%7Ctwcamp%5Etweetembed%7Ctwterm%5E1586378441548759042%7Ctwgr%5E35cdc9f38a25b3a116e5e6aab332dc64bcc993c%7Ctwcon%5Es1_&ref_url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.bloomberg.com%2Fnews%2Farticles%2F2022-10-29%2Frussia-halting-involvement-in-ukraine-grain-safe-transit-deal, accessed December 04, 2022.
41. Kusa, Iliya. 2022. "Turkey's Goals in the Russia-Ukraine War.". 12. 06. 2022, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/blog-post/turkeys-goals-russia-ukraine-war>, accessed December 17, 2022.
42. Kutchner, Jacob. 2022. "Agricultural Exports Revenue (2022) Declines for Ukraine Amidst Ongoing War.". 30. 12.2022, <https://www.chemanalyst.com/NewsAndDeals/NewsDetails/agricultural-exports-revenue-2022-declines-for-ukraine-amidst-ongoing-war-14073>, accessed January 04, 2023.
43. Martin, Nik. 2022. "Ukraine war: Russia blocks ships carrying grain exports." 17.03.2022, <https://www.dw.com/en/ukraine-war-russia-blocks-ships-carrying-grain-exports/a-61165985>, accessed December 23, 2022.
44. Massoud, Adla. 2023. "Black Sea grain initiative has reached 'dead end', Russia's Lavrov says.". 26. 04. 2023, <https://www.thenationalnews.com/world/us-news/2023/04/25/black-sea-grain-initiative-has-reached-dead-end-russias-lavrov-says/>, accessed May 14, 2023.
45. McCarthy, Simone. 2022. "No path to peace: Five key takeaways from Xi and Putin's talks in Moscow.". 22. 03. 2023, <https://edition.cnn.com/2023/03/22/europe/china-xi-russia-putin-talks-five-takeaways-intl-hnk-mic/index.html>, accessed April 24, 2023.
46. Meatcommerce. 2022. "Russian agricultural exports up 12% in 2022.", 08. 12. 2022, <https://meatcommerce.com/news/russian-agricultural-exports-up-12-in-2022-443544>, accessed April 24, 2023.
47. Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine. 2022. "The official position of the Ministry of Infrastructure regarding recent Russia's statement to withdraw from the Initiative for the safe transportation of grain and foodstuffs from Ukrainian ports.". 29 10 2022, <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/en/news/official-position-ministry-infrastructure-regarding-recent-russias-statement-withdraw-initiative-safe-transportation-grain-and-foodstuffs-ukrainian-ports>, accessed November 23, 2022.

48. Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation. 2022. "Foreign Ministry statement on the Black Sea Grain Initiative for the export of Ukrainian grain.". 29. 10. 2022, https://www.mid.ru/ru/foreign_policy/news/1835797/?lang=en, accessed December 07, 2022.
49. Novak, Gregor. Aust, Helmut. 2022. "The Law of Treaties in Wartime: The Case of the Black Sea Grain Initiative.". 10.11.2022, <https://www.justsecurity.org/84051/the-law-of-treaties-in-wartime-the-case-of-the-black-sea-grain-initiative/>, accessed November 18, 2022.
50. Office of Foreign Assets Control of the Department of the Treasury. 2022. "General License No. 6b Transactions Related to Agricultural Commodities, Medicine, Medical Devices, Replacement Parts and Components, or Software Updates, the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Pandemic, or Clinical Trials.". 14. 07. 2022, https://home.treasury.gov/system/files/126/russia_gl6b.pdf, accessed November 24, 2022.
51. Olchowski, Jakub. 2022. "The Black Sea grain game.", IES Commentaries No. 731 (243/2022) | 23.11.2022, <https://ies.lublin.pl/en/comments/the-black-sea-grain-game/>, accessed December 12, 2022.
52. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. 2022. "The impacts and policy implications of Russia's aggression against Ukraine on agricultural markets." 05. 08. 2022, https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/agriculture-and-food/the-impacts-and-policy-implications-of-russia-s-aggression-against-ukraine-on-agricultural-markets_0030a4cd-en, accessed December 17, 2022.
53. Pearson, Robert W. 2022. "Turkey between Ukraine and Russia.". 28. 03. 2022, <https://www.mei.edu/publications/turkey-between-ukraine-and-russia>, accessed November 12, 2022.
54. President of Russia. 2022. "Meeting with African Union Chairperson, President of Senegal Macky Sall.". 03. 06. 2022, <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/68564>, accessed January 15, 2023.
55. President of Russia. 2019. "The law ratifying the agreement between Russia and Egypt on comprehensive partnership and strategic cooperation.". 02. 08. 2019, <http://www.en.kremlin.ru/acts/news/61221>, accessed April 24, 2023.
56. President of Russia. 2022. "Vostok-2022 strategic command post exercise.". 06. 09. 2022, <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/69288>, accessed April 04, 2023.
57. Prokopenko, Alexandra. 2022. "What's in the Ukraine Grain Deal for Russia?", 26.07.2022, <https://carnegieendowment.org/politika/87576>, accessed December 12, 2022.
58. Radio France International. 2022. "US says no restrictions on farm equipment to Russia.", 14. 07. 2022, <https://www.rfi.fr/en/international-news/20220714-us-says-no-restrictions-on-farm-equipment-to-russia>, accessed December 29, 2022.
59. Reuters. 2022a. "EU to soften sanctions on Russian banks to allow food trade.". 19. 07. 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/eu-soften-sanctions-russian-banks-allow-food-trade-2022-07-19/>, accessed November 01, 2022.
60. Reuters. 2022b. "Explainer-How UN plan for Russian ammonia export could help global fertiliser market.". 14. 09. 2022, <https://www.yahoo.com/lifestyle/explainer-un-plan-russian-ammonia-180036030.html>, accessed December 07, 2022.
61. Reuters. 2022c. "Russia's statement on resuming participation in Black Sea grain deal.". 02. 11. 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/world/russias-statement-resuming-participation-black-sea-grain-deal-2022-11-02/>, accessed November 22, 2022.
62. Reuters. 2022d. "Kremlin says UN gave assurances on Russian exports in grain deal.". 17. 11. 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/kremlin-says-un-gave-assurances-russian-exports-grain-deal-2022-11-17/>, accessed November 24, 2022.
63. Reuters. 2023a. "Russia says it will only renew grain deal if its own exports are unblocked.". 01. 03. 2023, <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/russia-says-it-will-only-renew-grain-deal-if-its-own-exports-are-unblocked-2023-03-01/>, accessed April 24, 2023.

64. S&P Global. 2022. "Sanctions against Russia – a timeline.". 21. 12. 2022, <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/news-insights/latest-news-headlines/sanctions-against-russia-8211-a-timeline-69602559>, accessed December 29, 2022.
65. Shay, Shaul. 2018. "Russia and Egypt signed a "comprehensive cooperation and strategic partnership agreement.". October 2018, IPS Publications, <https://www.runi.ac.il/media/fusgnha/shaulshayrussiaegypt28-10-18a.pdf>, accessed March 21, 2023.
66. Siegle, Joseph. 2022. "The future of Russia-Africa relations.". Foresight Africa. Top priorities for the continent in 2022, Africa Growth Initiative at Brookings, February 2022, https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/foresightafrica2022_fullreport.pdf, accessed November 12, 2022.
67. Soylo, Ragip. 2022. "Russia-Ukraine war: Turkey seeks 25 percent discount from Kyiv over grain deal.". 07. 06. 2022, <https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/russia-ukraine-war-turkey-seeks-grain-discount-kyiv>, accessed January 23, 2023.
68. TASS. 2022. "Efforts made to connect Russian Agricultural Bank to SWIFT — Russian Foreign Ministry.". 16. 12. 2022, <https://tass.com/economy/1551609>, accessed November 24, 2022.
69. Tharoor, Ishaan. 2022. "Turkey's awkward role in the Russia-Ukraine war.". 20. 05. 2022, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/2022/05/20/turkey-ukraine-erdogan-russia-nato/>, accessed November 12, 2022.
70. ThyssenKrupp. 2022. "Ammonia in agriculture: The engine of plant growth.". <https://www.thyssenkrupp.com/en/stories/sustainability-and-climate-protection/ammonia-in-agriculture:-the-engine-of-plant-growth>, accessed November 07, 2022.
71. U.S. Embassy in Egypt. 2022. "The Ambassadors of Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the United Kingdom, the United States, and the EU in Cairo.". 01. 03. 2022, <https://eg.usembassy.gov/g7-ambassadors-we-must-stand-with-ukraine/>, accessed March 11, 2023.
72. U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission. 2022. "China's Position on Russia's Invasion of Ukraine.". 09. 12. 2022, <https://www.uscc.gov/research/chinas-position-russias-invasion-ukraine>, accessed April 04, 2023.
73. UkrAgroConsult. 2022. "TOP-10 countries-buyers of Ukrainian grain.". 03. 02. 2022, <https://ukragroconsult.com/en/news/top-10-countries-buyers-of-ukrainian-grain/>, accessed January 04, 2023.
74. UN News. 2022a. "Ukraine: Guterres welcomes departure of first grain ship, to help ease food crisis.". 01. 08. 2022, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/08/1123702>, accessed December 09, 2022.
75. UN News. 2023a. "Black Sea Grain Initiative extended on deadline day.". 18. 03. 2023, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/03/1134762>, accessed May 01, 2023.
76. UN News 2023b. "Russia confirms participation in grain deal for at least 60 more days.". 17. 05. 2023, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/05/1136757>, accessed May 20, 2023.
77. UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. 2022. "Press Release by the Joint Coordination Centre, Black Sea Grain Initiative.". 01. 08. 2022, <https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/press-release-joint-coordination-centre-black-sea-grain-initiative>, accessed December 07, 2022.
78. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. 2022. "The Black Sea Grain Initiative: What it is, and why it's important for the world.". 22. 09. 2022, <https://unctad.org/news/black-sea-grain-initiative-what-it-and-why-its-important-world>, accessed November 07, 2022.
79. United Nations Türkiye. 2022. "Black Sea Grain Initiative is renewed.". 18. 11. 2022, <https://turkiye.un.org/en/208017-black-sea-grain-initiative-renewed>, accessed December 16, 2022.

80. US Department of State. 2022. "US Sanctions on Russia.". 13. 07. 2022, <https://www.state.gov/briefings-foreign-press-centers/us-sanctions-on-russia>, accessed November 24, 2022.
81. Watson, Cameron. 2022. "Metis Insights: Black Sea Grain Initiative Analysis.". 26. 07.2022, <https://channel16.dryadglobal.com/metis-insights-black-sea-grain-initiative-analysis>, accessed January 05, 2023.
82. Wehrey, Frederic. 2022. "What the Russian War in Ukraine Means for Libya.". 26. 03. 2022, <https://en.minbarlibya.org/2022/03/26/what-the-russian-war-in-ukraine-means-libya/>, accessed January 15, 2023.
83. White House. 2022. "Fact Sheet: Joined by Allies and Partners, the United States Imposes Devastating Costs on Russia.". 24. 02. 2022, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2022/02/24/fact-sheet-joined-by-allies-and-partners-the-united-states-imposes-devastating-costs-on-russia/>, accessed December 19, 2022.
84. Wiśniewska, Iwona. 2022. "Russia returns to the grain deal.". 03. 11. 2022, <https://www.osw.waw.pl/en/publikacje/analyses/2022-11-03/russia-returns-to-grain-deal>, accessed November 12, 2022.
85. Wiśniewska, Iwona. Wilk, Andrzej. Matuszak, Sławomir. Michalski, Adam. 2022. "Russia: renewed blockade of Ukrainian grain exports by sea.". 31. 10. 2022, <https://www.osw.waw.pl/en/publikacje/analyses/2022-10-31/russia-renewed-blockade-ukrainian-grain-exports-sea>, accessed November 06, 2022.
86. World Nuclear News. 2022. "Construction begins for El Dabaa unit 2.". 21. 11. 2022, <https://www.world-nuclear-news.org/Articles/Construction-begins-for-El-Dabaa-unit-2>, accessed March 21, 2023.
87. Zhen, Liu. 2022. "China says US sanctions over Ukraine should not affect right to trade with Russia.". 28. 02. 2022, <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/diplomacy/article/3168725/china-says-us-sanctions-over-ukraine-should-not-affect-lawful>, accessed December 04, 2022.